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International Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities

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- To contribute to policy, education, and community development by linking academic knowledge with practice.
- To foster dialogue between different cultural, social, and intellectual traditions globally.

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Original Research Paper

Enugu State Journalists Knowledge and Adoption of AI Fact Checking Tools in Combating Fake News

Ositadinma Jane Ogbu¹ | Prof. Michael Ukonu²

^{1,2} Department of Mass Communication, Faculty of Arts, University of Nigeria (UNN) Nsukka

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*Corresponding Author:

Ositadinma Jane Ogbu

*Email:

janiecj68@gmail.com

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Abstract: Artificial Intelligence (AI) has become a significant force shaping contemporary journalistic practice. This study explored the level of awareness among journalists in Enugu State regarding the use of AI-powered fact-checking tools in addressing the spread of fake news. It also examined the extent to which these tools are being adopted, as well as the challenges faced in their practical application. Adopting an exploratory survey design, the study gathered data from 57 journalists registered with the Nigerian Union of Journalists (NUJ), Enugu State, through a researcher-designed questionnaire. The findings revealed that journalists in the state demonstrated a strong understanding of AI-based fact-checking technologies and actively employed them in their professional routines to counter misinformation. However, the study also identified key obstacles to effective use, including high operational costs, inadequate training on tool utilisation, and limited institutional support from media proprietors.

Keywords: Fact Checking Tools, Artificial Intelligence, Fake News, Journalists, Enugu State

Background of the Study

Al-Zoubi and Ahmad (2024) describe Artificial Intelligence (AI) as a transformative innovation significantly impacting the field of journalism. AI encompasses a range of technologies that enable machines to perform complex operations typically associated with human cognition, such as reasoning, learning, decision-making, verification of facts, language translation, and speech recognition. Over time, AI has evolved into a dominant force influencing various spheres of human activity—spanning social, political, academic, and economic landscapes. Presently, AI is largely associated with machine learning systems capable of replicating human thought processes and refining outputs based on algorithmic learning (Oginni, 2024, p. 75).

In the context of growing digital

platforms—ranging from news websites to social media and data-driven journalism—Al-Zoubi and Ahmad (2024) argue that journalism's dependence on advanced technologies is on the rise, and that AI will significantly redefine journalistic practices and elevate content quality and distribution (Khan, 2024). Radcliffe (2025) highlights that journalists are increasingly integrating AI into their workflow for tasks such as content drafting, editing, transcription, verification, and research. Citing a Pakistani editor, Radcliffe (2025) suggests that AI offers powerful tools that can enhance productivity and transform how journalistic content is developed and delivered.

From information gathering to writing and eventual publication, AI can be seamlessly embedded in all stages of news production, alleviating workload pressures for journalists.

Oginni (2024) characterises AI as a ground-breaking innovation with the potential to redefine the media landscape. According to Hashemi-Pour (2024), a growing proportion of digital content is now generated with AI assistance. Beyond text, AI tools also support the creation of multimedia content, including audio and visuals, which are often used for blog articles, email campaigns, and social media posts (Hashemi-Pour, 2024). As such, tools like ChatGPT, Grammarly, Otter, and Canva are becoming essential in newsrooms due to their efficiency and ability to stimulate creativity (Radcliffe, 2025).

Although AI-driven fact-checking services are generally regarded as beneficial in curbing fake news and misinformation, DeVerna, Menczer, Yang, and Yan (2024), referencing findings from Indiana University, caution that these tools may, paradoxically, reinforce belief in false narratives or reduce confidence in factual ones. Endert (2024) notes that generative AI introduces new complications to the problem of disinformation. Free and unregulated AI platforms allow users to manufacture deceptive content—including fabricated voices and manipulated visuals—at scale, blurring the line between real and fake (Endert, 2024; Adebajo, 2024).

AI can generate original text, audio, video, or imagery from a prompt, or alter existing media to produce misleading outcomes, including deepfakes that convincingly replicate human behaviour (Adebajo, 2024). Hashemi-Pour (2024) warns that improper use of such technologies can jeopardise public trust, invade privacy, and distort factual reporting. DeVerna et al. (2024) stress that unintended consequences can emerge when the public interacts with AI-generated content without oversight.

Shin (2024), drawing on data from NewsGuard, reports a tenfold rise in AI-generated fake news websites in 2023, many of which operate with minimal or no human involvement. Khan (2024) observes that AI has become a tool for amplifying disinformation, particularly during politically sensitive periods. She cites the example of

global elections, where malicious actors deploy fake videos, audio, and images to manipulate public opinion. Shin (2024) also points out the difficulty in distinguishing these fabricated materials from authentic reports.

DeVerna et al. (2024) acknowledge the excitement surrounding the potential for AI to support large-scale fact-checking operations, especially in an environment where human reviewers struggle to keep pace with misinformation proliferating online—including content created by AI itself. Despite its benefits in improving journalistic efficiency and accessibility, Radcliffe (2025) notes that AI introduces serious risks, including the erosion of journalistic integrity. Shin (2024) and Endert (2024) argue that the technology facilitates mass production and distribution of deceptive media, which can influence key events such as elections and conflicts through propaganda and misinformation.

In the Nigerian context, the media space has not been spared from the consequences of AI-powered misinformation. Numerous fake news stories and AI-generated disinformation campaigns have targeted political figures and government institutions. Despite this, Nigerian media organisations have invested significant effort in combating these threats. For instance, on July 21, 2021, a false report—accompanied by images—claimed that an Air Peace aircraft crashed in Ilorin, Kwara State. After investigation, the Nigerian Civil Aviation Authority confirmed the report was entirely fabricated, intended to damage the airline's reputation.

Another example is a video released by Boko Haram alleging the downing of a Nigerian Air Force Alpha Jet on March 31, 2021. Although the footage depicted a plane crash over a forest in Borno State, military investigations later confirmed that the crash was caused by adverse weather conditions, not enemy fire. Similarly, a Facebook post dated February 18, 2021, by the proscribed Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB), claimed that the group had shot down a Nigerian Air Force helicopter in Orlu, Imo State. The

accompanying image showed a burning helicopter, but this was promptly refuted by the Air Force, stating that no such incident occurred.

Despite the dangers posed by the misuse of AI, it is important to acknowledge its potential for good. Khan (2024) raises a pertinent question: Can the same technology that spreads falsehoods also be leveraged to counter them? According to Shin (2024), collaborations among researchers, technology firms, and governments are underway to use AI as a tool to combat AI-driven misinformation. While addressing AI-generated disinformation remains a priority for media institutions worldwide, this study investigates how journalists in Enugu State understand and utilise AI-powered fact-checking tools in their efforts to detect and prevent fake news and misinformation.

Statement of Problem

The rapid evolution of information and communication technologies has significantly expanded public access to media platforms, particularly through digital and social media. This shift has, however, contributed to a sharp rise in the spread of misinformation and fake news. Dumebi (2020) notes that even Nigeria's mainstream media have been implicated in disseminating unverified information, which has, in some cases, aggravated conflicts such as the farmer-herder crisis. One notable example cited was a report circulated by several prominent media outlets in June 2018, claiming that Danladi Ciroma, a leader of the Miyetti Allah Cattle Breeders Association, had justified attacks in Plateau State as retaliation for the loss of cattle, and allegedly issued threats of further violence if the animals were not recovered. This highlights the on-going difficulty in promptly identifying and countering misleading narratives before they escalate into broader social unrest.

Conventional fact-checking techniques often struggle to keep pace with the speed and scale of misinformation online, thereby necessitating more advanced and responsive tools. Artificial Intelligence (AI)-powered

fact-checking technologies have emerged as potentially transformative in verifying information more quickly and reliably. Nevertheless, the implementation and impact of these AI-based tools in the African media landscape, particularly in Nigeria, remain underexplored and require systematic evaluation.

Recognising the global concern around fake news, Jacob (2022) points out that some media organisations have begun integrating fact-checking strategies to restore audience trust and promote accurate journalism. Against this backdrop, the present study seeks to investigate the extent to which journalists in Enugu State are familiar with AI-enabled fact-checking tools, the degree to which they employ them in their work, and the barriers they face in doing so.

Objectives of the Study

1. To examine the level of awareness and understanding of fact-checking tools among journalists in Enugu State as a means of combating fake news.
2. To assess the extent to which fact-checking tools are adopted by journalists in Enugu State.
3. To identify the major challenges faced by journalists in Enugu State when using fact-checking technologies to address misinformation.

Research Questions

1. What is the level of knowledge among journalists in Enugu State regarding fact-checking tools as a means of combating fake news?
2. To what extent have journalists in Enugu State adopted fact-checking tools in their reporting practices?
3. What challenges do journalists in Enugu State encounter when using fact-checking technologies to curb fake news?

Review of Similar Literatures

While a growing body of literature explores the broader functions of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and its role in modern journalism, relatively few studies focus specifically on the application of AI-powered

fact-checking tools in combating the spread of misinformation and fake news. This study critically reviews available literature that examines how AI is transforming journalism practice globally and within Africa.

One relevant study is by Oginni (2024), investigated the Role of Artificial Intelligence in Journalism in Nigeria. Grounded in the Technology Acceptance Model, the research adopted a descriptive survey approach and engaged 150 purposively selected journalists using a structured questionnaire. The study found that AI tools significantly enhance journalistic productivity by improving the efficiency and accuracy of news reporting. These tools were also credited for streamlining editorial workflows in media organisations.

Similarly, Stanescu (2023) studied the Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Journalism with the aim to explore both the opportunities and challenges associated with AI in journalistic content production. The study found that while AI currently supports journalists in simplifying routine tasks, there is concern that, with advancements in automation, such tools may eventually displace human professionals in certain newsroom functions.

Talabi et al. (2024) investigated the adoption of AI in news gathering and reporting within Nigerian mass media, focusing on Lagos Television (LTV) and Television Continental (TVC). Using in-depth interviews with journalists from both stations, the study explored how AI is utilised in data analysis, content automation, and news writing. Findings indicated an increasing reliance on AI for content production and editorial support. However, the study also highlighted the need for ethical oversight and regulatory frameworks to ensure responsible use.

In an international context, Noain-Sanchez (2022) examined the perception of experts, Journalists, and Academics regarding the Impact of artificial intelligence on Journalism. The research involved in-depth interviews conducted over two phases (2019

and 2021) with professionals from the United States, United Kingdom, Germany, and Spain. The findings suggested that AI technologies improve newsroom productivity by accelerating news production and reducing the workload of journalists. However, the study also identified a lack of AI literacy among journalists and recommended increased training and ethical oversight to mitigate emerging concerns around misinformation and automated reporting.

Another relevant study is by Adjin-Tettey, Muringa, Danso, and Zondi (2024), who explored the integration of AI in journalistic practices in Ghana and South Africa. Conducted through qualitative interviews with 18 journalists, the study revealed that most newsrooms in both countries had not fully institutionalised AI tools in their workflows. Instead, individual journalists use AI for basic tasks like transcription, research, story generation, and fact-checking. The study identified key barriers to adoption, including financial constraints, language limitations, and resistance to change. Additionally, ethical concerns such as misinformation and attribution challenges were highlighted, with respondents suggesting more training and ethical guidelines as potential solutions.

Theoretical Framework

This study adopts the Technological Determinism theory, originally proposed by Marshall McLuhan in 1962. The theory posits that technological advancements are a key force in shaping societal structures and human behaviour. It suggests that as media technologies evolve, they influence how individuals think, interact, and engage with society. Within the context of this study, technological determinism helps explain how the rise of AI is altering journalistic practices—from information gathering and writing to fact-checking and dissemination. While AI presents potential threats to traditional journalism, it also offers tools that can enhance efficiency and reduce workload.

Research Methodology

This research employed an exploratory survey design to investigate the awareness

and usage of AI-based fact-checking tools among journalists in Enugu State. The aim was to determine how journalists are leveraging these technologies to combat misinformation and promote credibility in their reporting. Data were gathered through a self-designed questionnaire, tailored to capture both quantitative and qualitative responses.

The questionnaire was designed to be straightforward and user-friendly, consisting of both closed- and open-ended questions. This allowed respondents to express detailed opinions while also providing structured responses for easy analysis. Physical administration of the questionnaire was conducted by the researcher and trained assistants who visited media organisations across Enugu State.

Population and Sample Size

The study population comprised journalists registered with the Nigerian Union of Journalists (NUJ), Enugu State chapter. According to official NUJ records, the total number of registered journalists in the state is 57. As such, the study adopted a census approach, surveying all 57 journalists from various media outlets in the state.

Method of Data Analysis

Responses collected from the 57 participants were systematically analysed and presented using frequency tables and percentages. This descriptive statistical approach allowed the researcher to identify patterns in the respondents' knowledge

levels, adoption rates, and perceived challenges regarding AI fact-checking tools.

Findings and Discussion

The results revealed that a significant number of journalists in Enugu State possess substantial knowledge of AI-driven fact-checking tools. Furthermore, the data showed a high level of adoption of these tools in their professional routines, particularly in identifying and curbing the spread of fake news. Despite the widespread usage, participants reported several challenges, including technical limitations, lack of training, and concerns over the reliability and ethics of some AI applications. These findings are consistent with existing literature, which underscores both the transformative potential and ethical complexities of AI in journalism.

Research Question One: *What is the level of knowledge among journalists in Enugu State regarding fact-checking tools as a means of combating fake news?*

The findings from Research question one revealed a high level of awareness of fact-checking tools among journalists in Enugu state. The findings revealed that the journalists in Enugu state have the knowledge of AI-powered applications that can be utilised by journalists in their day-to-day routines, especially in checking facts before disseminating information, and that these applications can serve as tools for combating fake news.

Table 1: Frequency and Percentage of Respondents' Knowledge of AI Fact-Checking as a Tool in Combating Fake News

Question	Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Do you know about fact-checking apps?	Yes	53	93.0
How well do you know about these apps?	Very Well	49	86.0
Can these apps combat fake news?	Yes	51	89.5
How can these apps combat fake news?			

The question "how can these apps combat fake news?" allowed the participants to freely express their opinions. The inputs from the participants revealed that training of

journalists on the proper usage of these applications, constant monitoring of the usage of the applications and cross-checking of AI-generated leads and stories before

dissemination can go a long in combating fake news dissemination.

Research Question Two: *To what extent have journalists in Enugu State adopted fact-checking tools in their reporting practices?*

The findings from the research question two revealed a high adoption level of AI fact-checking applications as a tool in combating fake news among journalists. The findings

revealed that although the journalists in Enugu state used AI in their different routines – such as fact-checking, generating story ideas, researching, developing story angles, translations, etc. – they would easily opt for the traditional fact-checking method, more than the AI fact-checking applications. The reason being that the journalists feel that fact-checking is an important function of journalism which is too important to be left at the mercy of just the computer.

Table 2: Frequency and Percentage of Respondents' Adoption of AI Fact-Checking Applications in Combating Fake News

Questions	Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Do you utilise AI in your routine?	Yes	52	91.2
In what routines do you use AI?			
Can fact-checking apps combat fake news?	Undecided	49	86.0
Do you use these tools in fact-checking?	Some Times	39	68.4
Give reason for your previous answer.			

One the question “in what routines do you use AI?” the following journalism routines took majority of the votes by the respondents: translations, transcription, generating story ideas and leads, researching, developing story angles, generate news stories, grammar-checking and fact-checking. On the request for the participants to give reasons for their answer on a previous question, the inputs from the majority of the respondents were collated, studied and interpreted thus: although AI fact-checking applications can be a veritable tool in combating fake news and journalists

in Enugu state have already subscribed to the use of these applications in curbing the spread of fake news, the journalists however, feel insecure while leveraging on the powers of these AI applications as they believe that the traditional fact-checking method provides for a more credible and efficient journalism.

Research Question Three: *What challenges do journalists in Enugu State encounter when using fact-checking technologies to curb fake news?*

Table 3: Frequency and Percentage of Problems Encountered by the Journalists While Utilising Fact-Checking Applications in Curbing Fake News

Problems	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Cost of procuring the apps	45	78.9
Problems with translations to local languages	50	87.7
Poor training on app usage	54	94.7
Low supervision by media owners	48	84.2
What do suggest in salvaging this issue?		

On the question “What do you suggest in salvaging this issue?” the inputs by the participants, having been carefully studied, reveals that journalists in Enugu state feel

that if journalists should undergo extensive training on the usage of these AI applications, and if the media owners constantly supervise how journalists

incorporate these applications in their daily routine, then a more credible and efficient journalism can be assured. The journalists also suggest that AI application developers salvage the issue of language translations, and as well make these applications easily affordable.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Conclusion

The study assessed the knowledge of journalists in Enugu state on AI fact-checking applications as a tool in combating fake news, as well as the level of their adoption of these AI applications in combating fake news. The study also reviewed the challenges the journalists in Enugu state encountered while using the AI fact-checking applications in curbing fake news. 57 registered journalists in Enugu state were sampled, and the information obtained was carefully studied. Hence, this paper concludes on the note that although AI impacts so much on journalism practice and that journalists in Enugu state are already incorporating AI applications in their daily routines, there are still a lot to be done in other to ensure credible AI-powered journalism in Enugu state.

Recommendations

From the findings obtained from the study, this paper recommends that:

1. Supervision of the usage of AI fact-checking applications is made a top priority by media owners. This will ensure that AI applications are used properly to ensure that journalists maintain the ethics of journalism in the discharge of their duties.
2. Training sessions is organised for journalists and other media practitioners on workings and usage of AI applications. This will give journalists and other media practitioners a level of control over the incorporation of these applications in their daily routines.
3. Journalists ensure ethical usage of AI applications in their daily routines. This will ensure AI-based ethical journalism practice, which not only limits the work load of journalists, but ensures fast information access and dissemination while promoting credible journalism.
4. AI application developers address the geographical issues associated with the applications, which provide the foundation as to why the AI applications cannot translate local languages. This will ensure the development of AI applications that will work perfectly in any location, hence a veritable tool for journalists across the globe.

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